

ASSEMBLY METHOD USED IN MANUFACTURING 3D AUXETIC CELLULAR STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Auxetic means that the material or structure possesses negative Poisson's ratio. Auxetic materials own many fascinating properties due to the negative Poisson's ratio character, such as increased shear modulus, indentation resistance, fracture toughness, energy absorption, porosity/permeability variation with strain, synclastic curvature and so on. Recent years, 3D non-random auxetic cellular structures have attracted considerable interest and become a focus of auxetic material research. Though, due to the complexity of their configuration, to our knowledge, most 3D ordered auxetic cellular structures can only be manufactured by additive manufacturing method. However, additive manufacturing method will introduce some defects to the structures such as rough surface, irregular cross sections, and defects caused by stair stepping effect. Additionally, mass production and cost are also problems for additive manufacturing method, and the materials can be used are also limited by the additive manufacturing equipment.

In this paper, a novel manufacturing method of one type of 3D auxetic structure will be briefly introduced. For this method, the structure was divided into 2D parts which can be easily manufactured by traditional fabricating methods with high-accuracy. The present manufacturing method will overcome the shortcomings introduced by additive manufacturing methods; in other words, the quality of the structures will be improved compared with additive manufacturing methods. At the same time, it will expand the range of materials that can be used to manufacture 3D auxetic structures. Additionally, this manufacturing method has the potential for mass production and automatic manufacturing while keeps the manufacturing costs at low level. Also, numerical simulation was conducted to simulate the structure's Poisson's ratio, and the negative Poisson's ratio character was successfully demonstrated.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Poisson's ratio of a material is defined as the ratio of the lateral contractile strain to the longitudinal tensile strain for a material undergoing tension in the longitudinal direction. [1] And it is named after Simeon Poisson. [2] To our daily experience, when a material is stretched, such as an elastic band or elastic bar, the material will not only become longer in the stretching direction but will also become thinner in the lateral direction (the material will become thinner in the lateral direction while become longer in the pulling direction); conversely, it will expand laterally when the material is compressed in the longitude direction. That is to say, the material owns positive Poisson's ratio. It seems that, all materials we encountered possess positive Poisson's ratio. But classical elasticity theory tells us that the variation scopes of Poisson's ratio are from -1 to 0.5 [3] for three dimensional (3D) isotropic materials and from -1 to 1 for two dimensional (2D) isotropic systems [4] based on thermodynamic consideration of strain energy [5]. For anisotropic materials, the value range of Poisson's ratio could be even larger [6]. All the theories imply the possibility of materials with negative Poisson's ratio. The materials with negative Poisson's ratio are called negative Poisson's ratio (NPR) material or auxetic material, and the word auxetic comes from Latin which means expand. Actually, many auxetic materials have been discovered long before. [7-9] But extensive researches on auxetic materials were from the seminal work done by Lakes [10], in which they introduced a three-step manufacturing method of auxetic foams from conventional open-cell foam.

Since Lakes' work, vast researches on auxetic materials have been done because of the fascinating properties introduced by the negative Poisson's ratio effect, such as increased shear modulus, [11] indentation resistance, [12,13] fracture toughness,[10,14] energy absorption (ultrasonic, acoustic, damping), [15-17] porosity/permeability variation with strain,[18-20] synclastic curvature[21]. Due to the improvement of these properties, auxetic materials have great potential for many applications fields such as textiles, industry, aerospace, protection, biomedical, sensors and other sectors. [22]

Recent years, 3D ordered auxetic cellular structures have attracted considerable interests and become a focus of auxetic material research. Due to the development of 3D print technology, many complicated 3D auxetic cellular structures can be manufactured. Schwerdtfeger et al [23-25] designed and fabricated a series of 3D auxetic structures from Ti-6Al-4V through SEBM, and then study their dependence of Young's modulus on relative density and Poisson's ratio property. Li et al [26] designed another type of 3D auxetic lattice structures based on the 2D re-entrant lattice structures, and fabricated them from Ti-6Al-4V through electron beam melting (EBM) process; then study their properties. Andreassen et al [27] used topology optimization in designing the structure and manufactured it in polyamid using SLS selective laser sintering (SLS). Bückmann et al [28] designed and fabricated macroscopic polymer structures by three-dimensional printing and microscopic samples by direct laser writing (DLW) system, and also evaluated and characterized the material. Bückmann et al [29] have also designed and fabricated mesoscopic auxetic structures by DLW.

From the researches of 3D ordered auxetic cellular structures introduced above, we can see that 3D ordered auxetic cellular structures were mainly manufactured by 3D printing like manufacturing method due to their complicated structure. However, 3D printing like manufacturing method will introduce some defects to the structure such rough surface, [26] irregular cross sections, [26] and the stair stepping effect [24] will also do harm to the structure. What's more, mass production and cost are also problems for 3D printing like manufacturing method and the materials can be used are also limited by the 3D printer. In this paper, a novel manufacture method which adopts the interlocking concept will be briefly introduced. This method will overcome the defects mentioned above and greatly facilitate the mass production and automatic manufacturing of the auxetic structures, at the same time it will greatly reduce the manufacturing expenses. In addition, this novel method is suitable for any kind of material that can be adhesive bonded (materials such as plastic) or welded (materials such as metal). Also, numerical simulation was conducted to simulate the structure's Poisson's ratio, and the negative Poisson's ratio character was successfully demonstrated.

2 THE STRUCTURE

The 3D auxetic structure studied in this work is extended from the 2D re-entrant auxetic structure proposed by Warren [30], and Li [26] has manufactured the structure using EBM process. The 2D and 3D structures are shown in Fig.1. For both the 2D and 3D structures, they are consisting of vertical strut and oblique strut in a re-entrant manner.

Fig.1 2D and 3D re-entrant auxetic structures: (a) 2D re-entrant auxetic structure (b) 3D re-entrant auxetic structure

For the 2D re-entrant auxetic structure, the unit cell can be described in terms of three primary design parameters as shown in Fig.2a: length of the vertical struts (H), length of the re-entrant struts (L) and the re-entrant angle (θ). For the 3D re-entrant auxetic structure, there need to be four more parameters; they are the dimensions of the vertical strut and oblique strut including width (t_1) and thickness (t_2) of the vertical strut as well as width (t_3) and thickness (t_4) of the oblique strut as shown in Fig.2b.

Fig.2 Parameters for 2D and 3D re-entrant auxetic structures: (a) Parameters for 2D re-entrant auxetic structure (b) Parameters for 3D re-entrant auxetic structure

3 THE NOVEL MANUFACTURING METHOD

Though the development of additive manufacturing technology has allowed the manufacturing of structure of any shape, it has unavoidable defects as mentioned above. So, we devote to manufacturing the structure with traditional manufacturing method. Based on the fact that the 3D structure was extended from the 2D structure as well as our team has manufactured many lattice cores using the interlocking concept. We have tried to use the interlocking concept, and finally we have invented the interlocking process that can be used in manufacturing 3D auxetic cellular structures. In the interlocking process, the 3D auxetic structure has been divided into reentrant 2D parts, and it is easy to manufacture 2D structures with conventional machining methods.

To verify the feasibility of the interlocking process, $5 \times 5 \times 3$ unit cell samples were built using PVC polymer. After the 2D PVC parts were manufactured, they were interlocked and bonded with ethyl α -cyanoacrylate adhesive (General purpose glue 502 adhesive produced by Shandong Yuwang Industrial Co.,Ltd chemical branch). The parameter values for design configuration are as follows: $H=18\text{mm}$, $L=9\text{mm}$, $t_1=t_2=t_3=t_4=2\text{mm}$ and the reentrant angle $\theta=50$ degree.

Fig.3 Polymer 3D auxetic specimen manufactured using the interlocking assembly method

The structure was successfully manufactured with the interlocking assembly method as shown in Fig.3. From the pictures, it can be seen that the specimen manufactured using the interlocking assembly method owns smooth surface and regular cross sections.

4 NUMERICAL SIMULATION

Numerical simulation was performed for compression test using the finite element analysis software ABAQUS to evaluate and probe the Poisson's ratio character of the structure. A convergence study was performed to ensure that a mesh was chosen that gave an accurate result within a reasonable calculation time. During simulations, hex structured C3D8I element was used. The lower end of the structure was fixed and a given displacement load was applied on the upper end, as the boundary condition settings and load conditions of the simulations. The FE model for compression tests is depicted in Fig. 4. To calculate the Poisson's ratio of the structure, the displacement in x-direction of the nodes in the center of the outmost vertical strut in the center layer of the samples was exported.

Fig.4 The FE model of the compression test.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Sample dimensions and mass

The measured values of the width and depth as well as the struts size both vertical and re-entrant of the samples are determined by the machine used to produce the parts, and their measured values have hardly any differences with the designed. Only the heights and masses of the samples were slightly difference with the designed. The measured heights are slightly higher than theoretical, which are expected to be caused by the interlocking errors; and we can see that the discrepancy between theoretical and measured is rather small. The masses values are also higher than the intended one, and the increased mass are considered to be the mass of the adhesive used to bonding the interlocking nodes.

5.2 Poisson's ratio

From the simulation result of the compression test, it can be seen that the structure will contract laterally when compressed, which means that the structure owns negative Poisson's ratio character. From the definition of Poisson's ratio and the strains both along the compress direction and the laterally direction, the Poisson's ratio can be obtained. And the Poisson's ratio of the structure is -0.40.

Fig.5 Simulation result of the compression test, displacement in x direction.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The interlocking method that can be used in manufacturing 3D auxetic cellular structures has been briefly introduced, and this manufacturing method has great advantages compared with 3D printing like method. We successfully built a series of samples using this method. We were able to demonstrate the auxetic nature of the structure by numerical simulation of compression test.

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